

3,4-Dichloro-2-thienyl-lithium, -Magnesium Bromide and -Copper and 3,4-Dichloro-2,5-dilithiothiophene from 3,4-Dichlorothiophene

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3,4-Dichlorothiophene undergoes M-H-exchange reactions with both *n*-butyllithium and ethylmagnesium bromide to give 3,4-dichloro-2-thienyl-lithium and -magnesium bromide respectively in high yields. With two equivalents of *n*-butyllithium, 3,4-dichlorothiophene gives 3,4-dichloro-2,5-dilithiothiophene in at least 71% yields. Metathesis of 3,4-dichloro-2-thienyllithium with copper(I) chloride in THF gives the corresponding copper compound in excellent yield. Some derivatives of these organometallics are described.

IN connection with our studies concerning the synthesis of thermally stable monomer compounds^{1,2} we needed 3,4-dichloro-2-thienyl-metallic reagents. We reported³ previously that the reaction of 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene (I) with metallic magnesium gives an equimolar mixture of trichloro-2-thienylmagnesium halide (II) and 3,4-dichlorothiophene (III) but not the desired 3,4-dichloro-2-thienylmagnesium halide (IV) as the end product. The latter is actually formed as an intermediate which undergoes a rapid metal-hydrogen exchange with the unreacted 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene giving the observed products II and III³.

The reaction of 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene with alkyl lithium reagents does not give 3,4-dichloro-2-thienyllithium instead it gives exclusively trichloro-2-thienyllithium⁴.

We now describe the preparation of 3,4-dichloro-2-thienyllithium, -magnesium bromide and -copper and 3,4-dichloro-2,5-dilithiothiophene from 3,4-dichlorothiophene in 74-82% yields.

Experimental

The reactions were carried out under a positive pressure of dry, oxygen-free nitrogen. The ethereal solvents were dried over sodium wire and distilled prior to use from sodium-benzophenone ketyl. *n*-Butyllithium in hexane was from Foote Mineral Co. and was used at the strength determined by the supplier. Ir spectra were taken as Nujol mulls using a Perkin Elmer Model 21 spectrometer. ¹H nmr spectra were recorded in CCl_4 , using a Varian A60 spectrometer. TMS was used as an internal standard for the nmr spectra. The glc analysis were carried out on an F and M Model 500 Gas Chromatograph using a $4' \times \frac{1}{8}''$ column packed with 15% Silicone Gum Rubber on chromosorb W (60-80 mesh). The yields were based on the starting amount of 3,4-dichlorothiophene. All temperatures quoted are uncorrected.

Preparation of 3,4-dichlorothiophene

The 3,4-dichloro-2,5-dilithiothiophene⁵ prepared from tetrachlorothiophene (0.25 mole) and *n*-butyllithium (0.5 mole) in ether (200 ml) at 0° to -5° was hydrolysed with dilute hydrochloric acid. The organic material was extracted with ether, the ether layer washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the solvent distilled and a yellowish liquid was obtained. This on fractional distillation under reduced pressure gave 3,4-dichlorothiophene, 24.8 g, (65%), b.p. 95°/38 mm, n_D^{20} 1.5755 (cited⁶: b.p. 182.01°, n_D^{20} 1.5762). The ir spectrum had the following major absorption bands at cm^{-1} : 3096 (aromatic C-H); 1499, 1486, 1414, 1404 and 1344 (polychlorothiophene nucleus) and 851, 781 and 679 (C-Cl). ¹H nmr spectrum shows a singlet at 2.9 τ (thiophene nuclear protons).

An attempted lithium aluminium hydride ($2x$ moles)-reduction of tetrachlorothiophene (x moles)

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in refluxing ether for 4 days did not give any 3,4-dichlorothiophene but gave only 2,3,4-trichlorothiophene in roughly 25% yield (glc).

3,4-Dichloro-2-thienyllithium

To 3,4-dichlorothiophene (25.0 mmoles) in ether (100 ml) at -15° was added over a period of 15 min *n*-butyllithium (25.0 mmoles) in hexane. Within 15 min Colour Test II⁷ was negative but Colour Test I⁸ was strongly positive. An aliquot was withdrawn, hydrolysed, extracted with hexane and examined by glc. 3,4-Dichlorothiophene was the only product. Chlorotrimethylsilane (5.4 g, 50 mmoles) was then added to the lithium reagent and the mixture stirred at 0° for 1 hr. Colour Test I was negative within one-half hour. The products were hydrolysed with dilute hydrochloric acid and the organic matter was collected in benzene. The benzene layer was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the solvent distilled and a brownish liquid was obtained. Fractional distillation under reduced pressure gave 2-(trimethylsilyl)-3,4-dichlorothiophene, 3.95 g (71%), b.p. 84° – $86^{\circ}/1.5$ mm, n_D^{20} 1.53580. Calc. for $C_7H_{10}Cl_2SSi$: Si, 12.47%, found: Si, 12.50%. ¹H nmr showed two singlets: one at 2.72 τ (thiophene nuclear proton) and the other at 9.68 τ (SiMe₃) in the integrated ratio of 1 : 9.

Table 1 gives the details of the preparation of 3,4-dichloro-2-thienyllithium and its carboxyl derivative under various conditions.

3,4-Dichloro-2,5-dilithiothiophene and 3,4-dichloro-2-thienylmagnesium bromide: The experimental details for the preparation of these reagents and their derivatives are described in the Table.

3,4-Dichloro-2-thienylcopper and its acetyl derivative

To 3,4-dichloro-2-thienyllithium, prepared in THF at -78° from 3,4-dichlorothiophene (12.5 mmoles) and *n*-butyllithium (12.5 mmoles), was added freshly purified¹² anhydrous copper(I) chloride (12.5 mmoles) and the mixture was stirred at -78° for 16 hr. Colour Test I⁸ was negative within 10 hr. The clear but faintly green coloured reaction mixture was then warmed to 0° , acetyl chloride (25 mmoles) added, and the resulting solution was stirred for 4 hr. The customary work-up¹³ and purification by column chromatography (silica gel, hexane as eluant) gave a white solid (2.05 g, 84%), m.p. 49° – 50° . Recrystallisation from hexane (60° – 70°) gave 1.8 g (74%) of methyl (3,4-dichloro-2-thienyl) ketone, m.p. 53° – 54° (cited¹⁰: 54°). ¹H nmr spectrum showed two singlets: one at 2.53 τ (thiophene nuclear proton) and the other at 7.4 τ (–CO–CH₃) in the integrated ratio of 1 : 3.

Reaction of 3,4-dichloro-2-thienylcopper with pentachloriodobenzene

To a THF-solution of 3,4-dichloro-2-thienylcopper, prepared from 3,4-dichloro-2-thienyllithium (25.0 mmoles) as above, was added pentachloriodobenzene

TABLE 1. THE PREPARATION OF 3, 4-DICHLORO-2-THIENYL-LITHIUM, -MAGNESIUM BROMIDE AND 3, 4-DICHLORO-2, 5-DILITHIOTHIOPHENE REAGENTS

I mmoles	RM mmoles	Solvent ml	Reactn. temp., $^{\circ}C$	Time of addn., min	Time of reactn., hr	Derivatizing agent	Products, % yields
12.5	<i>n</i> -BuLi 12.5	Ether 70	-15	15	2	CO ₂ *	V [¶] , 82
12.5	<i>n</i> -BuLi 12.5	THF 70	-78	15	2	CO ₂	V [¶] , 80
25.0	<i>n</i> -BuLi 25.0	Ether 100	-15	30	2	Me ₃ SiCl†	VI, 71
12.5	<i>n</i> -BuLi 26.5	Ether 100	0 to -5	30	6	Me ₃ SiCl	VI, 24£ VII , 71£
12.5	EtMgBr ¹¹ 15.0	THF 100	27	15	5	CO ₂	V [¶] , 32
12.5	EtMgBr 4 × 12.5	THF 100	27	15	5	CO ₂	V [¶] , 79‡

* Large excess of solid CO₂ was added in bulk for carbonation experiments. The work-up procedure was as described previously (ref. 9).

¶ M.p. 186° – 187° (ethanol-water); reported m.p. of V is 187° – 188° (ref. 10).

† For trimethylsilylation two equivalents of Me₃SiCl were added (see ref. 9 for working up).

£ Estimated by glc; all other products were estimated by weighing after separation.

|| For comparison an authentic sample of VII was prepared as described in ref. 9.

‡ VII was not formed when an aliquot from this reaction was reacted with excess Me₃SiCl.

(25.0 mmoles) in dioxan (130 ml). The lower boiling solvents were distilled off and the mixture heated in an oil bath at 100° for 40 hr. The reaction mixture was hydrolysed with ammonium chloride-aq. NH₃ solution and the organic material was collected in benzene. The benzene extract was washed with NH₄Cl-aq. NH₃ until all copper halides were removed, and then washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and the solvent distilled. The white solid obtained was chromatographed (silica gel column, hexane as eluent) to give (i) deca-chlorobiphenyl, 0.5 g, 12.5%, m.p. 308°–309° (cited¹⁴: 310°), mixed m.p. with an authentic sample was undepressed and (ii) (3,4-dichloro-2-thienyl) pentachlorobenzene, 5.4 g, 54%, m.p. 119°–120° (from CCl₄). The ¹H nmr spectrum showed one singlet at 2.657 (thiophene nuclear proton). Calc. for C₁₀HCl₇S: Cl, 61.8%; found Cl, 61.97%.

Results and Discussion

The 3,4-dichloro-2-thienyllithium reagent has been prepared both in ether and THF by metalating 3,4-dichlorothiophene (I) with one equivalent of *n*-butyllithium. No evidence for a metal-halogen exchange was observed. The lithium reagent was characterised by converting it to 3,4-dichloro-2-thenoic acid (V) (82%) by carbonation, and to 2-(trimethylsilyl)-3,4-dichlorothiophene (VI) (71%) by reaction with chlorotrimethylsilane.

3,4-Dichlorothiophene reacts with two equivalents of *n*-butyllithium in ether to give, subsequent to derivatisation with chlorotrimethylsilane, VI and 2,5-bis(trimethylsilyl)-3,4-dichlorothiophene (VII) in 24 and 71% yield, respectively. No positional isomers of the silylated products were formed. The formation of VII indicated the formation of 3,4-dichloro-2,5-dilithiothiophene in at least 71% yield. This dilithium reagent may also be prepared in over 90% yield from the easily accessible tetrachlorothiophene and two equivalents of *n*-butyllithium⁵.

3,4-Dichlorothiophene is metalated by ethylmagnesium bromide giving 3,4-dichloro-2-thienylmagnesium bromide. When one equivalent of ethylmagnesium bromide is used the yield of the carbonation product (V) is 32%. The yield rises to 79% when four equivalents of ethylmagnesium bromide are employed. In neither case was a di-Grignard reagent formed. It appears, therefore, that to get a

reasonably good yield of 3,4-dichloro-2-thienylmagnesium bromide, a many-fold excess of ethylmagnesium bromide has to be employed. This may be a disadvantage in some preparative work because in the reaction mixture there will be present, in addition to the desired Grignard reagent, an excess of unreacted ethylmagnesium bromide. In view of its easy formation and high yield the 3,4-dichloro-2-thienyllithium, now available in both ether and THF, may be a reagent of choice for synthetic purposes.

3,4-Dichloro-2-thienyllithium, prepared in THF at –78° reacts with one equivalent of copper(I) chloride to give the 3,4-dichloro-2-thienylcopper reagent. The formation of this reagent is indicated by a negative response to Colour Test I⁸, its thermal stability and its reaction¹³ with acetyl chloride to give methyl (3,4-dichloro-2-thienyl) ketone (VIII) (74%). The copper reagent couples with pentachloriodobenzene to give (3,4-dichloro-2-thienyl) pentachlorobenzene (IX), a polychlorinated unsymmetrical biaryl, in 54% yield.

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